

The Need for Hotel Elderly's in Thailand

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ABSTRACT: This paper aimed to study 1) the need for hotel for elderly's in Thailand with the quantitative method, the questionnaire covered 400 samples of Thai Elderly Tourists with non-probability and accidental sampling. Then, the data were analyzed with descriptive statistics for the respondent's information and with the correlation and multiple regression to find out any concordances between the need for hotel Elderly's in Thailand strategies and elderly's in Thailand. The research indicated that 1) for the whole of the need, Facility (X_2) ($\beta = 0.425$, $\alpha < .01$) and Staff (X_3) ($\beta = 0.417$, $\alpha < .05$) had a statistically significant effect on the Elderly's in Thailand.

KEYWORDS - need; hotel elderly's.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tourism the quality in order to limit the competency in the tournaments [1] Causing the country to turn their attention and Give priority to quality tourism Including quality tourism management to accommodate tourists Quality too With the Association for the Promotion of Tourism Asia and the Pacific (PATA) said That quality tourism is tourism that conserves natural resources And tourists are interested Learning [2] tourism In addition, quality tourism is Tourism of Elderly traveler That does not focus on the rush Slow travel Focus on touch-based tourism. And learn to appreciate Therefore, the elderly tourists are a group Quality tourists that have become a tourist market that many countries focus on to attract Quality tourists to travel in their country As in Malaysia, granting the right Seniors from Japan can enter the country without a visa in order to Stimulating time Of this group of tourists who will Leading to economic development and growth Of the next country. [3]

The tourism industry is an industry with high growth. And generate income into Thailand as A large amount of such growth has affected the country's economic and social system as Thailand has Beautiful natural resources Has a cultural identity Traditions and way of life, including Have service potential Which is an opportunity to create tourism value It also affects growth. Of the labor market And distribution of prosperity to every region of the country [4] With And due to the social structure change with the increasing elderly people, the tourism industry Thai people have adapted to accommodate this change by targeting tourism target groups for Elderly tourists Which has a tourism model that focuses on creating quality experiences Profound Within tourist attractions Want to absorb, learn and create spiritual values for tourists Through activities Travel related to life, culture or nature [5] The elderly tourists are the most important tourist groups. One of the most important groups of the world Due to the increasing rate They are quick and have the power to spend on tourism. If considering the classification of tourists in groups The elderly, [6] provided information on the grouping of tourists. A variety of elderly groups such as [7] Has divided the elderly tourists into 3 groups Namely, 1) tourists for leisure, 2) tourists for long-term vacations, and 3) tourists. For health, [8] divided the elderly tourists into 3 groups according to the type of travel. 1) Groups that travel to visit relatives and acquaintances (Family Travelers) 2) Groups who like to plan their travel in advance. They like to do a variety of activities while traveling (Active Resters) and 3) groups that buy travel programs on a package basis [9] At present, Thailand has begun to focus on the elderly. Because in the future it is predicted that Thailand will have an aging population. The elderly in Thailand will account for 32.1% of the nation's population, or about 20.5 million

people in the year 2040. It can be seen that the aging society has become closer to Thai people. Compared to traditional Japanese society, public buildings that are designed for the elderly are inevitable with hotels or accommodations for the elderly.

Most hotels offer a wide variety of activities for travelers of various ages. The design that takes into account the elderly is very important and should be realized because in the future the elderly population will be one-fourth of the Thai population. In today's world, countries turned to study and realized the change of way. The structure of the population in entering the aging society is an issue that is of great interest. Both at the national and global level because it has widespread impact on the macro level such as Gross Domestic Product (GDP) Income per capita Savings And investment in the government budget Employment and labor productivity Also at the micro level Including the impact on various markets, products and services Especially in finance and health Preparation to support such changes It is an urgent matter for Important to Make a systematic plan and start working Advance Due to various measures Many respects But it takes time to implement to see tangible results.

As a result, hotel operators in Thailand have to strategies to reflect market trends and changing tourist behaviors. It is interested in doing research on the need for hotel for elderly's in Thailand to be a guideline for the development of cooperation in the tourism industry for hotel Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand business operators and to build confidence in Elderly foreign tourists.

II. OBJECTIVES/RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The objectives of this research article were to study the need for hotel for elderly's in Thailand.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The framework of this quantitative research is based on related concepts and theories to study the need for hotel elderly's in Thailand with details as follows.

Figure 1 Conceptual framework of this study

Research Methodology

Population and sample group

The population was Thai Elderly's Tourists in Thailand. The sample group consisted of 400 respondents by non-probability sampling and accidental sampling. The number was obtained by calculating the formula without the population at a 95% confidence level, and the sample size was set as follows

$$n = \frac{Z^2 P(1-P)}{E^2}$$

Where:

n = Size of the sample group

Z = Reliability level

P = Proportion of the population

E = Highest error value which will happen

The acceptance level was in accordance with the statistical significance level at 0.5

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2(0.5)(1-0.5)}{(0.05)^2}$$
$$= 384.16$$

The sample size was 385 respondents. However, 400 questionnaires were gathered by using a probabilistic sampling method between August - December 2020.

Research Instrument

The research tool was a questionnaire where the samples were asked individually to provide information about Strategies Hotel for Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand. The content consisted of 3 parts as follows.

Part 1: General information of the respondents, namely gender, age, and average monthly income

Part 2: Information on factors used in the analysis of the need for hotel elderly's in Thailand.

Part 3: Information on the concordance between the need strategies and the set of results to the Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand.

Data analyses

The data were collected by distributing questionnaires in the form of filling in information online to provide convenience and speed to comply with the situation of the COVID-19 outbreak.

The quantitative data were analyzed with descriptive statistics for the concordance between the strategies and the set of results to the need hotel for elderly's in Thailand by analyzing the correlation coefficient and stepwise multiple regression.

IV. RESULTS

Regarding general data of the respondents, the following were found:

For the general information of the respondents, it was found that 220 respondents, 60%, were female, and 180, 40%, were male. 187 respondents were between 60-65 years old, 43.50%. 137 of them were 66 - 70 years, 18.50%. There were 35 respondents aged 75-80 years, 17.50%, and were 28 respondents aged 81-85 years, 14%. For the age 85 and over, there were 13 respondents, 6.50%.

Most of the informants, For average monthly income, most of them had an average monthly income of 300,001 - 400,000 baht, 183, 41.50%. There were 40 respondents, 20%, who got 200,000 baht or more average monthly income. For 600,001 - 800,000 baht average monthly income, 128 respondents, 14%, were involved. There were 21 respondents, 10.5%, who got 500,000 - 600,001 baht average monthly income. For the respondents who got less than 700,000 baht average monthly income, it was 7, 3.5%.

The results of the analysis of the need for hotel for elderly's in Thailand.

The the need for hotel for elderly's in Thailand The hotel business in Thailand as a whole were Facility (X_2) ($\beta = 0.425$, $\alpha < .01$) and Staff (X_3) ($\beta = 0.417$, $\alpha < .05$) with a statistically significant effect, respectively. They could jointly describe the variance of the the need for hotel for elderly's in Thailand by 71.2% ($R^2 = 0.712$) and the forecasting equations for the the need for hotel that affected the success of the Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand. Among Thailand on the whole (Y) in standardized form was $Zy = 0.425ZX_2 + 0.417ZX_3$ Results of analysis of the need for hotel for elderly's in Thailand.

The need for hotel for elderly's in Thailand terms of cost retardation, it was found that Staff (X_3) ($\beta = 0.417$, $\alpha < .01$) affected the need for hotel for elderly's in Thailand with statistically significance. It could jointly explain the variance of the need for hotel that affected the s Hotel for Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand by 71.2% ($R^2 = 0.712$), and the equation for forecasting the need for hotel for elderly's in Thailand that affected the success of the need for hotel for elderly's in Thailand term of cost retardation (Y) in standardized form was $ZY = 0.425ZX_2 + 0.417ZX_3$.

V. DISCUSSIONS

The results revealed that overall the need for hotel for elderly's in Thailand The hotel business in Thailand as a whole were Facility (X_2) ($\beta = 0.425$, $\alpha < .01$) and Staff (X_3) ($\beta = 0.417$, $\alpha < .05$) with a statistically

significant effect, respectively. They could jointly describe the variance of the the need for hotel for elderly's in Thailand by 71.2% ($R^2 = 0.712$) and the forecasting equations for the the need for hotel that affected the success of the Thai Elderly Tourists in Thailand. Among Thailand on the whole (Y) in standardized form was $Z_y = 0.425Z_{X2} + 0.417Z_{X3}$ Results of analysis the need for hotel for elderly's in Thailand This was consistent with the concept of [10] Monitoring the motivation and activities of the elderly Before retirement age (50-64 years) and after retirement (65-98 years) among tourists using a questionnaire with The American sample found that a factor in which both groups were common was leisure activity. Recreation, in which the pre-retirement age has a need for activities that promote family coexistence; Retirement travelers pay more attention to price. And safety factor a lot [11] Tourism Business Development Model for the Elderly: Case Study Elderly in the central region " It consists of 8 components: (1) tourism operators play an important role in organizing (2) the tour guide's responsibility is to understand nature. And the psychology of the elderly (3) seeking the readiness of suitable tourist sites. The facilities Convenient for that tourist attraction (4) Good quality service is one of the contributing factors to satisfaction and Excellent service that meets the needs of the elderly (5) appropriate activities arrangement, organizing Activities that build relationships between each other (6) Entertainment for happiness is the creation of physical happiness. And the heart to enjoy And good for health (7) Pay attention to safety by providing The importance of transportation (8). Reliability in management. Marketing. Services that meet the needs of the elderly, find flaws for improvement and Development of tourism for the elderly [9] The nature of the tourism needs for It is divided into 4 areas: 1) health, 2) food, 3) accommodation, and 4) management of travel companies Addition Problems and obstacles in And the operation of tourism business development for For the elderly, 4 major problems were found. Namely, 1) problems from the health of the elderly, depending on the age range, including physical and mental health; 3) The problem from the guide still lacked understanding of the specific characteristics of the service to the group. Of the elderly and 4) problems related to health care services [12] Management of things And facilitating the hotel for elderly tourism in Thailand Issues at the hotel Should be taken into account in the management of The needs of the elderly are different from other tourist groups. In areas 1) physical, 2) health, and 3) social and emotional. And management of things Of convenience according to the concept Civil architecture Take into account the 7 design aspects: 1) equality 2) flexibility 3) ease of design 4) Safety, 5) Space, 6) Understanding, and 7) Help saving.

III. CONCLUSION

Tourism in Thailand is growing steadily. And there is high competition causing businesses to adapt and develop strategies to accommodate rapid change especially to meet the needs of diverse traveler which the elderly tourist group is considered a group of quality tourists and is and have the ability to access Technology, the elderly traveler is a popular group of time travel There are many days of rest and relaxation Education.

The market that businesses should pay attention to because there is more and more purchasing power. The increase of e the number of the world's elderly population It has resulted in a variety of changes in business types. Including tourism the elderly tourists are tourists who have high purchasing power, spend their time traveling longer than other tourists, focus on tourism and receive good quality services. Worth considering the price focus on tourism and receive good quality services. Worth it considering the price but not Need to be the lowest price, focus on their own satisfaction. Have time to decide where to go Travel and Service Therefore, careful consideration in making decisions on how to buy and use the service.

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